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S1 Experimental Procedures

S1.1 Fabrication of WellProbe device

The devices were fabricated from aluminum by micromachining (PICOMAX 60 CNC, Fehlmann, Switzerland).^[1] The final device has an external cylindrical shape of diameter 5.5 mm and length 20 mm. To allow internal channel junctions, part of the channels connect to lateral open grooves, which are later sealed with a shrinking tube (Distrelec, Switzerland): the tube is cut at a length of 15 mm and shrunk by heating with hot air at 200°C. For a scheme with all the dimensions of the head, refer to the technical drawings in S6.2.

S 1.2 On bench immunoassays

For on-bench immunoassays, we coated the microtiter plate (black walls, flat bottom, Greiner) with 50 µg/mL of IgG4 (Abcam). After 1 h, we washed the unbound antibody with PBS three times and performed a blocking step with 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) in PBS for 30 min. After a PBS wash, we incubated the plates with IgG labeled with FITC (Abcam) at 1 and 10 µg/mL for 1, 3 and 6 min. We performed a wash and imaged the signal using a GFP filter and 3 s of exposure time. Data analysis was done using a custom-made script in MATLAB.

S1.3 MFP-based immunoassays

WellProbe devices were mounted vertically by fitting them between two screwed parts of a 3D-printed holder. The holder was attached to micrometer-precision stages that allowed movement control in the three spatial directions. A 1/32" in tube was attached between each back inlet of the device and a flow-rate sensor (Sensirion) and another one between the sensor and a disposable pressurized reservoir. The flow-rate was controlled with the MAESFLO™ software from Fluigent with the feedback loop obtained from the sensor data and the pressure pumps (Fluigent). The system was primed with 70% ethanol followed by DI water and PBS to avoid bubble formation during experiments.^[2]

For Figures 3 and 4, we incubated the plate with IgG4 (50 µg/mL, Abcam) for 1 h and the excess was removed with a PBS wash. The surface was blocked for 30 min in 1% BSA in PBS and after the PBS washing, the head was introduced into the well of choice. A flow confinement of anti-IgG4 conjugated with FITC (Abcam, 10 µg/mL) was established for 1-6 min and washed with PBS for 1 min. Data analysis was done using a custom-made script in MATLAB.

S1.4 Preparation of arrays of spots

We used an inkjet spotter (GeSiM, Dresden) to create a circular pattern of spots on the bottom of the microtiter plate well. The spotter deposited 10 drops per spot of anti-IgG antibodies (at a rate of approx. 0.1 nL/drop), and 15 drops of anti-IgG2 and anti-IgG4 antibodies (Abcam), all at a concentration of 50 µg/mL in PBS. The spots were dried for 1h in a desiccator before using them.

S1.5 Washing of WellProbe device

To avoid cross-contamination between different experiments, the device was flushed with water at maximum pressure (1.5 bar) for 30s, then with ethanol for 1 min and finally again with water for 1 min. This combination removes the attached antibodies in the channel without damaging the device or the tubing. For a more intense wash, the ethanol wash can be replaced by bleach.

S2 Finite element simulations

S2.1 3D finite element hydrodynamic simulations of one and two aspiration apertures

We performed hydrodynamic FEM simulations (COMSOL Multiphysics v4.4) by defining the 3D geometry of the liquid below all the WellProbe mesas and the nearest surrounding immersion liquid. The inlet injection was set to 40 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ and the aspiration at 41 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, the latter distributed evenly between two apertures or setting the whole flow-rate in one of the two. The Navier-Stokes equations were employed considering non-compressible and Newtonian flows and stationary conditions. No-slip conditions were set to all physical boundaries, and an open boundary was set between the geometry and the rest of the stationary liquid in the well. The mesh of the geometry consisted of 57,035 mesh vertices and 153,157 tetrahedra.

As seen in the figure below, the profile of surface shear stress at the well bottom in the two perpendicular axes analyzed (either aligned or perpendicular to the axis of the apertures) are very similar both with one and two apertures. An equivalent situation is expected for all regimes under which the flow below WellProbe is laminar. Thus, the system can operate with a single outlet aperture without significant efficiency loss. This makes it particularly robust to clogging by debris or bubble formation. We nonetheless kept two apertures in the final geometry of the device to ensure a symmetrical shape of the flow confinement when its size is dynamically modified, as in Figure 4 of the manuscript. The differences in flow velocity between the two apertures can be seen in Figure S2, as the streamlines are oriented to either one or the two apertures. The effect is however not pronounced near the surface (5 μm from the surface), being prominent at higher planes, such as at 2 mm, as shown in the right panel of Figure S2. This has no detrimental effect on the assay as it does not affect surface velocities and thus surface kinetics. Rather, the increasing height of the mesas at the device tip is the reason for the radial distribution of velocities on the surface in spite of all the liquid being collected in a single or double aperture.

Figure S2. (Left panel) Shear stress profiles for one or two active aspirations. (Middle panel) Velocity of the flow and flow streamlines on the well surface (5 μm). (Right panel) Velocity of the flow and flow streamlines at 2 mm from the well surface.

S2.2 Radial finite element simulations of diluted species

2D-radial finite element numerical simulations coupled laminar flow and transport of species physics, together with a general form boundary PDE to model the surface reaction. All simulations were performed with COMSOL Multiphysics v4.4 (COMSOL, Inc., Burlington, MA). We modelled the system with axial symmetry of a revolving 2D cross section.

For the laminar flow, we considered the Navier-Stokes equations with an incompressible flow. The geometry of the system is given in Figure S3.

The boundary conditions were:

Surface 1: Inlet of constant inflow velocity of 3,4 mm/s (equivalent to 40 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$)

Surface 2: Outlet of constant outflow velocity of 0.1 mm/s

Surface 3: Inlet at zero pressure

All other surfaces were set as no slip walls ($\vec{u} = 0$)

Figure S3. Side cut of the microfluidic profile showing the flow velocities under the mesas and axis of symmetry.

For the transport of diluted species, we employed the convection-diffusion equation assuming a constant diffusion coefficient and an incompressible fluid:

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} - D\nabla^2 c + \vec{u}\nabla c = R \quad (1)$$

where R represents the 'sink' due to the transfer of species from the solution to the surface. This transfer of species was modelled assuming first-order Langmuir kinetics, with R equivalent to the binding rate of the analyte on the surface $R = -\frac{\partial b}{\partial t}$.

Figure S4. Side cut of the microfluidic profile showing the flow velocities under the mesas.

The boundary conditions were :

- Surface 1: $c = c_0$
- Surface 2: $\vec{n} \cdot (-D\nabla c) = 0$
- Surface 3: $c = 0$
- Surface 4: $-R = k_{on} c (b_m - c_s) - k_{off} * c_s$

For all other surfaces a zero flux was imposed. A global initial value of $c(t = 0) = 0$ was set for all the cross section.

S2.3 FEM estimation of kinetic values by fitting experimental results

By using the model illustrated in S4, we fit the data by fixing most values according to experimental parameters or literature values ($c_0 = 10 \mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, $D = 6.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ ^[3,4], $k_{\text{off}} = 1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and evaluating a 2D space comprising the affinity constant k_{on} and the concentration of binding sites on the well surface b_m .

Figure S5 shows the best-fit curves of bound ligands as a function of time with the results from Figure 3d at the concentration studied. From this, we estimated the two parameters of interest: $k_{\text{on}} = 4 \cdot 10^5 \text{ L}/\text{mol}\cdot\text{s}$ and $b_m = 3 \cdot 10^4 \text{ mol}/\text{cm}^2$.

Figure S5. FEM-best fit for the evolution of fluorescence signal over time for the different kinetic zones and an on-bench experiment. The error bars represent experimental standard deviations ($n=3$).

S3 Analytical models

S3.1 Calculation of depletion layer size under the mesas of WellProbe

We estimated the size of the depletion layer as approximately the distance from the substrate at which a particle requires an equal time to reach the surface by diffusion or escape the region by advection (Figure S6).^[5]

Figure S6. Scheme representing the movement of a particle under two kinetic zones.

The shear stress at the well bottom is a function of the horizontal distance from the aperture, or radius (R), the local height of the mesa (H) and the flow-rate (Q):

$$\dot{\gamma} = \frac{3Q}{\pi R H^2} \quad (2)$$

With this, the velocity of a particle at a distance (d) close to the center is given by:

$$u = \dot{\gamma} d \quad (3)$$

Below a given mesa of constant height, we can calculate the position of the particle due to advection as a function of time by integrating Equation 3. If the height H is constant and we consider an initial radius R_0 equivalent to the radius of the aperture, this results in:

$$R(t) = -\sqrt{\frac{6Qd}{\pi H^2} t + R_0^2} \quad (4)$$

From this, the time to travel a certain distance following the radial flow is directly:

$$t = \pi H \frac{R^2 - R_0^2}{6Qd} \quad (5)$$

Because the flow is perfectly laminar, a streamline at a distance d_1 from the surface below a mesa of height H_1 , when arriving at the region below the following mesa will change its distance to the surface to d_2 , which is linearly proportional to the new height H_2 . Generalizing:

$$d_i = d_{i-1} \frac{H_i}{H_{i-1}} \quad (6)$$

From Equations 4 and 5 we can calculate the total time for the particle to reach the end of any mesa by advection, as the addition of the time of transit through each previous mesa:

$$t = t_1 + \dots + t_{i-1} + t_i = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\pi}{6Q} H_i^2 \frac{R_i^2 - R_{i-1}^2}{\left(d \frac{H_i}{H_n}\right)} \quad (7)$$

Where R_i is the external radius of each considered mesa inner to the mesa of measurement n . In the case of diffusion, the time travelled by a particle is given by:

$$\delta = \sqrt{2Dt} \quad (8)$$

By the same effect seen in Equation 6, the distance travelled vertically in each mesa translates into a greater distance in the subsequent mesas, proportionally to the height of the mesa measured and the original mesa H_n/H_i . The total distance travelled in the vertical direction projects into a final total distance at the mesa of interest (n), considering the time spent in each mesa as given by Equation 5:

$$\delta^2 = 2D \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{H_n}{H_i} t_i \quad (9)$$

This distance δ is the size of the depletion layer at the end of mesa (n). Resolving we obtain:

$$\delta = \left(D \frac{\pi}{3Q} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{H_n^3}{H_i} (R_i^2 - R_{i-1}^2) \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (10)$$

Finally, because we are interested in calculating the value of the depletion layer in the middle diameter of the mesas and not their maximum one, for calculation purposes we replaced R_n with:

$$R_m = \frac{R_n + R_{n-1}}{2} \quad (11)$$

S3.2 Analytical estimation of characteristic assay times and gains provided by WellProbe

We consider first order reaction kinetics:

$$\frac{\partial b}{\partial t} = k_{on}c_s(b_m - b) - k_{off}b \quad (12)$$

Where b_m is the total concentration of binding sites on the surface, b is the surface concentration of bound molecules at time t , c_s is the concentration of analyte close to the surface and k_{on} and k_{off} are the forward and reverse reaction constants, respectively.

If we consider an ideal case of perfect transport, we can assume that the concentration of analyte on the surface is the same as in solution ($c_s = c_0$). In this case an analytic solution for Eq. 12 exists.^[6] The time to reach 95% of the binding of equilibrium conditions is about 3 times the characteristic time of adsorption:

$$t_{reaction} \approx 3\tau = \frac{3}{k_{on}c_0 + k_{off}} \quad (13)$$

In the case of a purely diffusive system, such as an MTP incubating on a static bench, a depletion forms with a size that increases with time $\delta \approx \sqrt{2Dt}$ (Eq. 8). We can use Fick's first law to approximate the rate of diffusion through the depletion layer and because of transport-limited conditions assume that all transported analytes react with the surface:

$$\frac{\partial b}{\partial t} \approx D \frac{c_0 - c_s}{\delta} \quad (14)$$

Where D is the diffusion coefficient. Because of the transport-limited conditions, we can assume c_s to be initially 0, but with time will progressively increase to reach a value of c_0 as the binding sites get saturated after a time $t_{diffusion}$. We assume here for simplicity that c_s follows a square root curve to reach a value of c_0 , in the form $c_0 = c_s \sqrt{\frac{t}{t_{diffusion}}}$. Integrating Eq. 14 we then obtain an estimated time to reach equilibrium for diffusion-driven assays:

$$t_{diffusion} \approx \frac{2}{D} \left(\frac{b_{eq}}{c_0} \right)^2 \quad (15)$$

Where the equilibrium density of bound analytes is:^[6]

$$b_{eq} = b_m \frac{Kc_0}{1 + Kc_0} \quad (16)$$

Thus, from Eq. 13, 15 and 16, we can estimate the ratio of assay times using on-bench diffusivity and perfect reaction-limited kinetics as:

$$\frac{t_{diffusion}}{t_{reaction}} \approx \frac{2b_m^2 K^2 k_{off}}{3D(1 + Kc_0)} \quad (17)$$

S4. Assay quality assessment

The three-signal zones obtained with WellProbe can be used to assess if the signal is quantifiable and free of artefacts. Figure S7 illustrates four possible scenarios. Figure S7a-I depicts a well-functioning assay in which the signal increases from zone 3 to 1. The assay is within its dynamic range and is transport-limited, thus benefiting from using WellProbe. In Figure S7a-II the signals are low and close to their LOD. Depending on the attained signal strength, zones 1 and/or 2 may still be used for quantitation, while an increase in flows would enhance the signal. In contrast, in Figure S7a-III saturation has occurred or the chemical system is not transport-limited. In the first case quantitation is not possible, as no longer in a range of linear relation between time exposure/analyte concentration and signal. In the second case, either the chemical system is not well suited for WellProbe (low transport-dependency, such as for small molecules), or lower flow-rates could be used, saving sample. In some cases, reaching saturation may nonetheless be unavoidable, particularly when multiplexing the detection of analytes at very different concentration ranges. In this case, our system allows for the use of a fourth zone, as shown in Figure 4 of the main manuscript. Finally, any pattern not corresponding to cases I-III would be considered an artifact, indicating that assay quality is low (e.g. Figure S7-IV). This could be due to several reasons, from defects in the surface patterning of the ligand, through problems with the flow during the experiment to artifacts in sample reading.

Figure S7. Schematic illustration of possible signal results in zones 1, 2 and 3, with an additional zone 4 in case III.

S5. Additional chemical characterization

S5.1. Calibration curve

Experimental procedure: we performed a calibration curve using WellProbe and standard on bench assays using a simple fluorescent immunoassay. Wells of a 96 well plate were incubated with 100 μL of mouse monoclonal anti-human IgG4 antibody (Abcam, Cambridge, UK) at 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in PBS for 60 min. The surface was then blocked using 1% BSA in PBS for 30 min. Next, the wells for the on bench protocol were filled with 100 μL of rabbit anti-human FITC labeled antibody at increasing concentrations (Abcam, Cambridge, UK), and incubated for 3 and 60 min. After the corresponding time, the wells were washed three times using PBS. The WellProbe protocol was performed using the same solution as on bench, for a total time of 3 min with a flow-rate of injection and aspiration of 40 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. A wash was performed with WellProbe by injecting PBS during 1 min, at the same flow-rate as the antibodies. All the conditions were performed in triplicates ($n=3$). A blank well was used to establish a background baseline, which was incubated with 1% BSA in PBS during the corresponding times, and washed using the same protocols as the rest of the wells, both on bench and using WellProbe. The fluorescence was measured using a Nikon inverted microscope and a Nikon Digital Sight DS-U3 camera with an exposure time of 3 s and a white balance of 1.50/1.70.

Results: Figure S8 shows the calibration curve for WellProbe and compares it with the on bench protocol for the lower concentration range. WellProbe shows better performance for the same assay times in all the conditions tested. On bench assay times of one hour show equivalent or slightly higher signal compared with WellProbe for analyte concentrations over ~ 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, while lower concentrations favor the probe (statistically significant at 0.15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). The limit of detection (LOD) was calculated with a linear fit in the range below 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ considering the detectable limit as 3 times the standard deviation. We estimated an LOD for WellProbe of 0.15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, while the LOD for the on-bench protocols was of 1.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for 3 min and 0.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for 60 min.

Conclusion: these results seem to indicate that WellProbe shows higher signal at low concentrations than the equivalent assay on bench at both 3 and 60 min. As compared with standard on bench assays, the LOD gains of the probe for the same incubation time are of one order of magnitude for the model immunoassay studied here, and still statistically superior with one hour incubation (20x the time).

Figure S8. Calibration curve for on bench at 3 and 60 min, and WellProbe at 3 min of incubation times ($n=3$).

S5.2 Comparison of ELISA test with WellProbe and on bench

Experimental procedure: we performed an Enzyme-linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) to compare the performance of WellProbe to a standard on bench assay at a relatively low concentration (100 ng/mL). Wells of a 96 well plate were incubated with 100 μL of mouse monoclonal anti-Human IgG2 Fc (Abcam, Cambridge, UK) at 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in PBS for 60 min. This was followed by a passivation step incubating rabbit serum (Abcam) diluted 1:200 in PBS for 30 minutes. Next, a solution of human IgG2 protein (Abcam) of 100 ng/mL in PBS was incubated by either flowing on the surface with WellProbe at 40 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ or pipette dispensing of 100 μL . The WellProbe protocol was followed by flowing rabbit polyclonal Ab to human IgG-HRP (Abcam) at 0.05 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in PBS for 5 min at 40 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. The on bench protocol consisted of a pipette-based washing 3 times with PBS followed by dispensing of 100 μL of the same IgG-HRP solution for an incubation of either 5 or 60 min. All wells were then manually washed with PBS three times and 100 μL of 1-Step™ Turbo TMB-ELISA Substrate Solution (ThermoFisher, Waltham, USA) were added to each for a 10 min incubation. The reaction was stopped by adding 100 μL of H₂SO₄ per well and the colorimetric signal was read with a plate reader (Tecan Infinite 200, Männedorf, Switzerland). The experimental conditions were performed in triplicates ($n = 3$).

Results: Figure S9 below shows a sketch of the molecular assay and the signal intensity obtained for each experimental condition. On bench results were significantly higher than baseline at both 5 and 60 min of incubation with the primary antibody but statistically identical for both times, showing a negligible increase in signal intensity with times longer than 5 min up to one hour. The 5 min incubation protocol with WellProbe performed significantly better than both on bench experiments, with an average signal intensity 7 times higher.

Conclusion: for ELISA assays aiming to quantify analytes at relatively low concentrations (<1 µg/mL) WellProbe seems to significantly outperform equivalent standard on bench assays at a fraction of the required incubation time, typically in the hour range.

Figure S9. Scheme of the immunoassay (left) and comparison of the signal of WellProbe and on bench using ELISA (right), n=3.

S5.3 Non-specific binding

Experimental procedure: we performed an immunoassay both on bench and with WellProbe to test non-specific binding. For the positive assay, wells of a 96 well plate were initially incubated with native human IgG4 protein (Abcam, Cambridge, UK) diluted in PBS at 50 µg/mL for 1h, followed by a passivation with an incubation of PBS 1% BSA for 30 minutes. The negative plates were only incubated with the passivation step, without IgG. Next, a solution of goat anti-human IgG FITC (Abcam, Cambridge, UK) of 10 µg/ml was incubated for 3 min either with WellProbe (at 40 µL/min) or pipette dispensing. This was followed by a washing step with PBS, 1 min at 40 µL/min with WellProbe, or 3 times pipette-based solution removal. All experiments were repeated 3 times (n=3).

Results: we used a relative high concentration of dispensed IgG to maximize any non-specific binding. As a result, the positive signals are already close to equilibrium using both WellProbe and the on bench protocol, as shown in Figure S10. The negative results show however that the on-bench signal is significantly higher than the baseline, indicating non-specific binding. The negative signal of WellProbe is statistically identical to the baseline, and significantly lower than the equivalent on bench signal.

Conclusion: In contrast to the pipette-based washing of standard on bench procedures, WellProbe applies a constant flow-rate over the assay region. Because of the resulting constant shear stress: (i) non-specific binding is minimized during the incubation step and (ii) the washing step is generally more intense, uniform and in principle more reproducible. As a result, non-specific binding is minimal, and this further improves the ratio of positive:negative signal with WellProbe as compared to on bench assays.

Figure S10. Comparison of positive and negative signal performed on bench and with WellProbe to evaluate non-specific binding.

S5.4 Binding curves for 50 µg/ml

Experimental procedure: Here, we used the same procedure as for Figure 3d. Briefly, we incubated the plate with IgG4 (50 µg/mL, Abcam) for 1 h and the excess analyte was removed with a PBS wash. The surface was blocked for 30 min in 1% BSA in PBS and after the PBS washing, the probe was introduced into the well of choice. A flow confinement of anti-IgG4 conjugated with FITC (Abcam, 10 µg/mL, flow-rate 40 µL/min) was established for 1-6 min and washed with PBS for 1 min.

Results: As seen in Figure S11, at this concentration there is a saturation of signal at all times and mesas, except the point at t=1min in mesa 3, statistically below the saturation level.

Conclusion: For the particular antibody-antigen pair used here, 50 µg/mL represents the upper limit of the quantification range, only measurable with very short incubation times and in the most external mesa (lowest shear stress). Nevertheless, as shown in Figure 4 of the manuscript, the addition of a 4th kinetic zone (mesa 4) would enable to push this quantitation limit further up, with controlled incubation times of a fraction of the time and minimal shear stress.

Figure S11. Calibration curves of An-Ag system at 50 µg/ml (n=3).

S6 Additional technical aspects

S6.1 Robustness to the presence of bubbles

Bubbles originated in microfluidic systems can disturb the flow and alter assay kinetics, compromising assay quality or impeding assay completion. Common solutions include bubble traps, the use of surfactants, degassing solutions prior to use or optimizing the geometry of the chip.^[2] In our system, the probe geometry ensures that bubbles coming from the injection aperture migrate towards the higher mesas due to drag and buoyancy forces (Figure S12). Close to mesa 4 the flow velocity is low except near the apertures as the streamlines focalize close to the aperture when far from the well bottom. Therefore, the presence of bubbles in these areas does not significantly affect the aspiration of the confined liquid. Furthermore, if a bubble blocks one of the apertures, the second one ensures the continuation of the flow keeping the radial flow on the well surface.

Figure S12. a) Flow confinement stability with the presence of two bubbles next to the injection and aspiration channels. b) Bright field image of one of the bubbles. c) Immunoassay performed under the presence of bubbles.

S6.2 Technical drawings of the WellProbe design used in this work

Figure S13. Dimensions of the specific WellProbe design used for all experimental work

S6.3 Spot configuration for multiplexed experiments

Maximum spot size is limited by mesa width, although large spots could potentially show an internal signal gradient due to intra-spot shear rate variations. This was not observed in this work with spots of 100 μm diameter. Smaller spot diameters could be used to fit more spots per circle and increase multiplexing, particularly under the smaller inner mesas. This is possible as long as the spot area is sufficiently large for the optical aperture of the reader. While in the present configuration the same spots were repeated in each circle, many other configurations are possible. This includes having spots specific to different analytes in every circle to increase multiplexing, placing spots in the inner or outer circles according to the expected analyte concentration or having spots with low ligand concentration in outer mesas and vice versa, to further increase the quantitation range.

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